

PROCESS MODELLING & DESIGN FOR RESIN TRANSFER MOULDING

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ABSTRACT

Growing interest in manufacturing technologies such as resin transfer moulding (RTM) and structural reaction injection moulding (SRIM) has led to the development of models to describe reinforcement deformation and resin flow. This paper describes the application of these models to RTM (including preform manufacture) and illustrates their use for a prototype component. Initial results are presented for a range of materials including reinforcement drape (using a kinematic model), fabric compaction and in-plane permeability. A mould filling prediction is included based upon a finite element/control volume method. The implications for mould design are discussed and the methods involved are identified as key elements in an integrated design strategy.

1. INTRODUCTION

Liquid moulding technologies¹ including RTM and SRIM are emerging as key strategies for volume production across a range of industries. Liquid moulding offers the advantages of low tooling costs relative to steel pressings combined with component integration to provide an effective solution for composite structures. In order to survive in a competitive field and to achieve the short concept-to-customer times demanded by the modern market, the manufacturer requires CAE systems which reduce lengthy development times traditionally associated with new parts. Predictive methods are becoming available for liquid moulding processes which, if combined with high quality material characterisation data, will enable manufacturers to proceed with confidence via integrated design methods.

Process modelling is central to the integrated design method. This is applied to both preform manufacture and subsequent processing. The preform needs to be designed to take account of structural loadings, deformation and drape of the reinforcement during preforming and resin flow during the impregnation phase. Conflicts may arise between these individual process requirements and effective preform design which takes each of these into account remains a key issue. Analysis of flow and cure within the mould can be carried out prior to the final mould design stage. For non-isothermal processes² heat transfer between the mould walls, the reinforcement and the incoming resin will be necessary. For all but the smallest RTM components, the polymerisation will need to be taken into account during the filling phase. During SRIM, the limited cycle times make this essential in all cases.

The design of the mould is critical to the success of the liquid moulding process and the quality of the final part. This is particularly true when considering shell moulds which possess neither the thermal capacity or structural stiffness of monolithic steel moulds. Structural design must ensure that the mould

body and supporting structure are sufficient to withstand clamping loads, pressure loadings arising from reinforcement compaction and fluid pressures. Thermal design must also be carried out to ensure that the mould heating system will be effective, that sufficient heat transfer can occur within the specified time frame to counter the effects of mould quench and resin exotherm and provide acceptable cycle times. The fluid flow characteristics determine whether a complete fill will be achieved, the time to achieve mould fill and the fluid pressure loadings on the mould surfaces. Resin flow will influence heat transfer within the mould which likewise affects viscosity, cure and flow behaviour while each of these factors may affect or be affected by the behaviour of the mould structure. Process modelling offers the only sensible approach to this complex problem.

The integrated design concept is shown in Figure 1. The need for iteration in the process is emphasised by the modified "waterfall" approach. The remainder of the paper describes the elements of the integrated design method with reference to techniques for data collection and the inter-relationship between the elements. Where appropriate, the methods have been demonstrated by considering a structural component. This is a prototype undershield for use in competition cars and is shown in Figure 2.

2. FIBRE REINFORCEMENT

Effective structural design requires specification of the service loads and performance criteria or material/structural properties together with cost specification. Traditionally this determines the laminate design but in an integrated design approach, this may only represent one stage of an iterative solution. Several reinforcement materials have been considered in the study:

1. Continuous filament random glass fibre mat (Vetrotex Unifilo U750-450)
2. Quasi-unidirectional stitch bonded glass fibre zero-crimp fabric (Tech Textiles E-LPb 567)
3. +/-45° stitch bonded glass fibre zero-crimp fabric (Tech Textiles E-BXhd 936)
4. +/-45° stitch bonded carbon fibre zero-crimp fabric (Tech Textiles C-BXhd 800)

The fibre architectures, fabric orientations and superficial density all influence the structural and processing properties of the preform. Subsequent sections consider how each aspect the processing properties may be evaluated together with how each influences the process or part quality.

3. PREFORM DEFORMATION

Before the reinforcement is loaded for injection with resin, it must be preformed. A kinematic draping algorithm has been applied to simulate the deformation of stitched bi-directional reinforcements or zero crimp fabrics. This is based upon the work of Mack & Taylor⁴ assuming that the only available mode of deformation is in-plane shear. To obtain a unique solution to the draping algorithm, two intersecting fibre paths must be constrained to the surface. These paths are determined by the reinforcement orientation and the component geometry. The draped position of each crossover point may then be calculated by solving the equations of intersection with the surface. In this simulation, the component geometry is represented using bilinear patches, allowing the equations to be solved explicitly.

This algorithm has been applied to an area of the Undershield shown in Figure 2. Figure 3 shows the draped fibre paths for a 0/90° reinforcement orientation. Figure 4 shows the fibre paths for a ±45° orientation. In both cases, preform wrinkling is predicted at the swage corners. This has been confirmed by experiment.

4. PREFORM COMPACTION

Preform compaction is an important factor in mould design and may represent a more significant loading than that of the fluid pressure during impregnation. Compaction relations for a range of reinforcements have been determined using a compression cage mounted on an Instron multi-tester at 20°C, 40°C and 60°C using 20 layers of reinforcement. Sample results are shown in Figures 5 and 6.

In all tests greater compaction of the reinforcement was seen at a higher temperature for the same applied pressure. Two reinforcements, Unifilo U750-450 and Tech Textiles 567 contained binder which softened during the elevated temperature trials producing a preformed specimen at the end of the test. At 60°C, a significant reduction in thickness was exhibited for the same compaction pressure, attributed to reinforcement shift which is facilitated by softening of the thermoplastic binder, film former and polyester yarn. Repeated testing of the same specimens indicated an apparent increase in compliance. The re-test curve converged upon the initial test data at the higher loadings as the reinforcement reached its maximum compression. In the preforming range associated with glass fibre reinforcements it is clear that repeated loading and unloading of a reinforcement will increase preform compaction.

5. PERMEABILITY MEASUREMENT

The permeability of the reinforcement defines the fluid flow characteristics in the mould and hence the fill pattern. Ply and stack permeabilities are thus important factors in laminate design and reliable characterisation data are essential to this. To maximise part performance a compromise may be necessary between the permeability, mechanical properties and mould design. Several individual reinforcements have been characterised using the methods described below.

A radial flow rig, Figure 7 has been used to measure the wetting permeability of a range of reinforcements. This method is more appropriate to liquid moulding than a steady state method which measures wetted permeability. A method described by Hirt et al⁵ is used to calculate the in-plane permeability of the anisotropic reinforcement from the length of flow path. An iterative solution provides the principal permeabilities k_1 and k_2 . The results for the range of reinforcements considered are shown in Figure 8. Some anisotropy is seen in each case.

The fibre volume fraction in each ply will differ according to the compressive modulus of the individual fabrics. The thickness of each layer thus the volume fraction of each material can be found for the corresponding clamping pressure. Prediction of local and global porosities and permeabilities requires use of the compaction data given above. Following determination of the ply permeabilities, the bulk permeability (assuming "plug" flow) of the stack can be estimated using an addition rule. The stacking sequence can be specified to provide acceptable permeabilities for a given fibre volume fraction and part performance. Unifilo U750-450 is placed in the mid-plane to promote rapid fluid flow in all directions. The relatively high bulk factor has the further advantage of maintaining compaction pressure in the mould cavity.

6. MOULD FILLING

The focus of an integrated design method for RTM components is the implementation of process understanding within a computer based package. This has been done by modification of a commercially available finite element program called PAFEC-FE³. The equations that govern the RTM process can be cast simply into an FE form. The basic physics of the fill phase of RTM is based on in-plane incompressible mass conservation and Darcy's law as a statement of the momentum balance. When proper initial and boundary conditions are imposed, upon a finite element model, the program is able to calculate a pressure field over any impregnated preform model. While concentrating on generally curved and thin components the methods can be extended to full three dimensional flow. To advance from one quasi-steady state pressure solution to the next, the control volume method is used. This is an analogous statement of in-plane mass conservation and is used to update fill front location.

Input data for the program are derived from physical properties of the preform and resin system. The preform is represented by principal permeabilities for each layer and the orientation of the principal flow direction with respect to another axis system. These permeabilities can then be summed on a layer by layer basis for each finite element in order to find an equivalent preform stack permeability for each element.

To demonstrate the potential of such an approach the undershield geometry was input to the flow analysis program. The geometry was obtained directly from the mould maker who used a CAD surface modeller to define the mould. The mould was cut using NC cutter paths produced from this CAD data. The component geometry was transferred using the defacto IGES format, to a dissimilar CAD package, where detail was removed and a FE model produced. Additional data required for FE flow analysis was added and the analysis performed.

Figure 9 shows the fill front locations for an analysis based upon isothermal impregnation of polyester resin injected under constant head of 6.5 bar (gauge) into 6 layers of Unifilo U750-450 CFRM by a central pin gate. The expected radial injection fronts develop into a predominantly one dimensional transverse flow across the mould. This has been confirmed by conducting a series of short shots which are shown in Figure 10. The model shown assumes a single pin gate. It is possible to investigate the effects of moving the location of this gate, of simulating multi-point injection situations, or of using weir and flood gates. During the flow analysis the fill program calculates pressure distributions behind the flow front. These pressures can be used to support mould design by transferring the fluid pressure loading to a structural analysis.

The ability to undertake more design early in the product cycle must increase the designer's awareness of the manufacturing process. The preform design affects the flow in the mould. The preform design also effects the structural performance of the finished component. The same FE model and preform orientation can of course be used to perform a stress, deflection and/or strength analysis on the part in service.

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Figure 2

Figure 3 : Half undershield draped with 0/90° reinforcement

Figure 4 : Full undershield draped with ±45° reinforcement

Figure 5 : Compaction data - U750-450 (Random E glass)

Figure 6 : Compaction data - E-LPb 567 (Unidirectional E glass)

Figure 7 : Radial permeability test (after Hirt et al)

Figure 8 : In-plane permeability - ply data and preform stack

Figure 9 : Fill front predictions for half-model of prototype undershield

Figure 10 : Short shot sequence